

Research Article

Hypo-T: A Statistical Tool that Enhances Hypothesis Testing Efficiency Using Guess and Check Method

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Abstract: Hypothesis testing is a critical aspect of statistical analysis, yet traditional methods often prove time-consuming and complex, leading to errors and misinterpretations. This paper introduces Hypo-T, an innovative statistical tool designed to enhance the efficiency of hypothesis testing through a user-friendly Guess and Check method. Hypo-T aims to simplify the formulation and evaluation of hypotheses, providing immediate feedback to users and fostering a deeper understanding of statistical relationships. The novelty of this tool lies in its iterative approach, which integrates real-time data analysis and advanced error-checking mechanisms to minimise Type I and Type II errors. Societal benefits include improved student educational outcomes and enhanced decision-making capabilities for researchers and industry professionals. Furthermore, Hypo-T has significant commercialisation potential, as it can be marketed through online platforms, making it accessible to a broad audience. By addressing the challenges associated with traditional hypothesis testing, Hypo-T aims to promote more efficient, accurate, and insightful data-driven decision-making, aligning with the Malaysian Education Blueprint's goals to advance national education in science and technology.

Keywords: Statistics; Hypothesis Testing; Educational Tool; Mobile Application; Educational Technology

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hypothesis testing is a fundamental component of statistics that influences decision-making and inferential analysis. It is a systematic procedure derived from the research question that analyses whether the findings of a research study support a certain theory that can be applied to the population. Hypothesis testing has applications in a variety of sectors, including social sciences, medicine, economics, science, engineering, and technology. Recent research has used hypothesis testing, for instance, to examine the factors affecting educational attainment (Kasi & Prasad, 2020), to identify a series of slices with the most significant COVID-19 symptoms in a CT scan (Chen et al., 2021), to

enhance hazard identification and improve system safety for risk management (Rashid, 2024), and to assess the efficiency of the stock market (Siahaan, 2023).

Implementing hypothesis testing can be challenging due to various factors. Based on preliminary observations, students often struggle with the hypothesis testing topic due to a lack of statistical background. When answering questions related to hypothesis testing, it can be difficult for them to identify the appropriate statistical methods. The p-values for the SPSS outputs are not all in the same table, which adds to the challenge. Additionally, dealing with missing values in the SPSS output poses another difficulty for them. This aligns with the finding of Shamsuddin et al. (2021), who also observed that many students struggled to understand the requirements of the questions linked to the hypothesis test, which consequently caused them to commit other errors, such as transformation and process skills.

Recent research highlights several suggestions for overcoming this issue, such as developing an innovative teaching and learning statistical tool that would facilitate the student's understanding of statistics more effectively, particularly on topics related to hypothesis testing (Shamsuddin et al., 2022). In their study, the authors introduce a guideline that uses Microsoft Excel to analyse and test hypotheses. Furthermore, to optimise learning, Smiderle et al. (2020) recommended using a game-based learning environment, where the objective of gamification is to enhance cognitive abilities (Kazimoglu & Bacon, 2020) and encourage students to advance their skills at their own pace (Liang et al., 2023). In addition, a study by Hafeez (2021) demonstrates that modern learning methods, including those based on games, computers, or mobile devices, are more effective and efficient than conventional learning approaches.

Although statistics might be difficult for students, it is essential to their education and future careers. This paper aims to integrate fun learning by introducing a game element to ignite students' imagination and engagement. Thus, the main goal is to design a statistical tool called Hypo-T that could provide guided hypothesis testing by demonstrating step-by-step processes for hypothesis formulation, testing, and interpretation using the guess-and-check approach. This is consistent with the Malaysian government's goals to transform the quality of education in Malaysia through the Malaysia Education Blueprint, which is intended to prepare Malaysia's workforce for the demands of a rapidly evolving and technologically advanced world.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The advent of "Hypo-T," a statistical tool designed to enhance the efficiency of hypothesis testing through the guess-and-check method, signifies a notable advancement in educational technology, particularly within the realms of interactive learning and mobile applications. This tool capitalises on user-friendly interfaces and visual aids, which have been shown to significantly improve student engagement and comprehension.

Recent studies have underscored the effectiveness of interactive learning formats, particularly infographics and video content, in educational settings. For instance, Lackmann et al. (2021) explored the impact of video formats on student engagement and performance, revealing that infographic videos tend to enhance learning outcomes compared to traditional lecture captures. Their findings suggest that the choice of video format can significantly influence student engagement, thereby affecting overall learning efficacy (Lackmann et al., 2021).

In addition to video formats, the preference for infographics over traditional text-based resources has been well-documented. Crick and Hartling (2022) found that infographics are perceived

as more engaging and memorable, facilitating better retention of information among students. This aligns with the work of Steyn et al. (2023), who reported that students in higher education overwhelmingly prefer infographics to plain text, indicating a shift towards more visually oriented educational strategies.

Moreover, the comparative effectiveness of infographics versus video formats has been a subject of considerable research. Kneer et al. (2022) highlighted that, while both formats can enhance learning, students often exhibit a preference for infographics due to their visual appeal and ease of comprehension. This preference is further supported by findings from Buljan et al. (2023), which indicated that infographic formats were rated higher in terms of user experience and knowledge retention compared to traditional summaries.

The future of digital tools for language mastery and statistical analysis appears promising, particularly in the context of mobile applications. Eremkina et al. (2023) demonstrated that digital infographic services significantly aid in vocabulary acquisition, showcasing the potential for such tools to enhance language learning. Furthermore, Criollo-C et al. (2024) explored the use of mobile applications in teaching indigenous languages, emphasising the importance of technological acceptance in educational contexts. Their research suggests that mobile applications can serve as effective platforms for both language mastery and statistical analysis, providing interactive and visually engaging learning experiences.

In conclusion, the innovations represented by "Hypo-T" and similar educational tools underscore the importance of interactive learning formats, such as infographics and videos, in enhancing student engagement and comprehension. The preference for these formats over traditional methods indicates a significant shift towards more visually oriented educational strategies, which are likely to shape the future of learning in both statistical analysis and language mastery.

3. METHOD & MATERIAL

This innovative product was developed as an automated process for conducting hypothesis testing using a specialised Excel template embedded within a PowerPoint presentation, which can be used in a classroom and offline and is called a system. The specialised Excel template was also transformed into an online tool by using the *Open As App* application. This product can be used online and offline in two different forms. The goal is to streamline and simplify hypothesis testing for researchers who may not be familiar with statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS) output.

Table 1. System Materials

	Materials	Description
1	Excel Template	A dynamic Excel file designed to automate the six steps of hypothesis testing.
2	PowerPoint Integration	The Excel template is embedded within a PowerPoint presentation to improve accessibility and ease of use during presentations or workshops. Users can input values generated by SPSS into the same table as the SPSS output table provided in the interactive notes. Since the SPSS output for each statistical method is presented differently, users can easily identify the relevant information.

3	Online Accessibility	The template is designed for online viewing, enabling users to access and utilise the tool conveniently from their smartphones by downloading and installing the <i>Open As App</i> .
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3.1 Data Input

Users key in the values displayed in SPSS output to the same table design in the interactive notes. The table template for each statistical method is formatted to match SPSS output tables, ensuring a seamless data transition.

3.2 Hypothesis Selection

Users select their specific hypothesis statement from the drop list option. For example, for the Independent Samples t-test, there are three options for the null hypothesis, which are $\mu_1 = \mu_2$, $\mu_1 \geq \mu_2$, $\mu_1 \leq \mu_2$. This selection guides the subsequent analysis steps.

3.3 Automated Analysis

The template efficiently processes input data to carry out the six steps of hypothesis testing. There are two approaches to decision-making based on either the p-value or test statistics. If the p-value is employed as the criterion, the steps are as follows: firstly, the statement of hypotheses; secondly, the specification of the distribution; thirdly, the determination of the significance level; fourthly, the calculation of the p-value; fifthly, the decision to either reject or fail to reject the null hypothesis; and finally, the conclusion contextualised within the research question. Alternatively, when using test statistics for decision-making, the sequence remains similar: the first step involves formulating the hypotheses; the second step specifies the distribution; the third step identifies the critical value(s); the fourth step involves calculating the test statistics; the fifth step entails deciding regarding the null hypothesis; and lastly, the conclusion should be articulated in relation to the research question.

3.4 Result Interpretation

The system offers clear, step-by-step guidance, assisting users in data analysis even if they are unfamiliar with interpreting p-values and their significance in relation to their hypotheses. This structured approach to hypothesis testing also aids students in business statistics in memorising each step through checks and estimations. Furthermore, the template is designed for seamless deployment as an app, enabling researchers to access the tool online. This feature enhances accessibility and promotes collaboration among users.

4. FINDINGS

This innovative product features over 20 common hypothesis tests, including the Independent Samples t-test, Levene's Test, Paired Samples t-test, and Chi-Square Test. The presentations of SPSS output for these statistical methods vary, allowing users to easily recognise them. This clarity is particularly advantageous for researchers conducting hypothesis testing, as the names of the statistical methods are clearly identifiable within the SPSS output. This functionality is especially beneficial for students, as repeated practice helps them remember the necessary steps. They can employ a guess-and-check approach, making an initial guess and then promptly verifying their answers through automated

feedback. Furthermore, an interactive gaming component is available to assist users in identifying statistical methods based on SPSS output. When addressing questions related to hypothesis testing, students can quickly identify the subtopic and the name of the statistical method before reading the question itself. Additionally, many questions in the assessments focus on information that is absent from the SPSS output table, encouraging students to locate these details. The system also provides the names of tables and formulas for each value, thereby enhancing the overall learning experience.

5. INNOVATION HIGHLIGHT

The unique features and advantages of the Hypo-T application are as follows:

- i. Support the Malaysian Education Blueprint (2013 -2025): The innovation of Hypo-T supports the Malaysian government's efforts in developing national education, particularly in the fields of science and technology as stated in the Malaysian Education Blueprint (2013-2025).
- ii. Instant Access and Feedback: The Hypo-T tool is a mobile application designed to provide seamless access and provide instant feedback on exercises to users.
- iii. Encourage Independent and Flexible Learning: Hypo-T provides guidelines, tutorials, and flexible learning opportunities that learners can access at their own pace.

6. COMMERCIAL VALUES

The Hypo-T has the potential to be commercialised through online shopping platforms such as Shopee and Lazada. These are the perfect places to approach potential customers from thousands of users of those platforms. Hypo-T has been registered under the intellectual property identification number LY2024S03740.

7. CONCLUSION

The development of the Hypo-T application provides step-by-step instructions to users to understand each stage of hypothesis testing. This can enhance learners' understanding of the hypothesis-testing topics. The instant feedback on exercises Hypo-T encourages students to quickly understand and correct their mistakes. The innovation of Hypo-T not only helped improve users' learning skills but also improved their critical thinking and analytical skills. In conclusion, Hypo-T represents a valuable tool for improving the accuracy and clarity of hypothesis testing.

Acknowledgements: The authors would like to express their gratitude to Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Sabah Branch for their support and resources in developing Hypo-T. They also extend their sincere thanks to the organisers of MAGiC 2024 (Malaysian Innovation and Games Exhibition) for providing an excellent platform to showcase this innovation. Their encouragement and commitment to promoting educational technology have been invaluable.

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